

LOD-GEOSS Deliverable D4

Using GEOSS and Copernicus for Energy Systems Analysis

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1 Introduction and Goals

This Best-Practice Guide is a result of the project Linked Open Data and use of the global earth observation system GEOSS in energy system analysis (LOD-GEOSS). The aim of LOD-GEOSS is to develop an interconnected database concept for input and result data of modelling in energy system analyses. In the area of energy research a large number of data is already available and is provided via standardized interfaces. So far these interfaces have hardly been used in energy system analysis. The goal of WP 4 is therefore to show within a Best-Practice Guide how these databases can be used.

Chapter 2 explains the concept of GEOSS and how the GEOSS Portal can be used. The following Chapters 3 and 4 contain examples for static and time-resolved data sets and how they can be accessed. First an ERA5 reanalysis data set will be presented in section 4.1. A description of two CAMS radiation data sets can be found in section 4.2. In the last section 4.3 the deterministic and probabilistic forecasts from ECMWF will be described and it is shown how to get access to these forecasts, which will later be use in the demonstrator of evaluating the forecats in deliverable "Demonstration and Best Practices" ([Hoyer-Klick et al. 2023](#)) in chapter 6.

2 GEOSS

The Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS) is built by the Group on Earth Observations (GEO). In 2003 on the G8 summit in Evian, the need for a coordination of Earth observations was agreed. Two years later at the third Earth observation summit in Brussels almost 60 countries joined the GEOSS 10-Year Implementation Plan ([GEO 2020a](#)). Since then the number of nations and organizations who support GEO and GEOSS is constantly growing. At this point more than 100 national governments and organizations work together in the GEO network. The goal is to improve the observation of the Earth with financial, political, and technical support and also with a better management of the existing data ([ECMWF n.d.b](#)).

Many institutions and scientific groups are providing data bases and portals which are related to Earth observation. Users can find on many different sides, data, images and analytical software packages that help them working on topics in the area of biodiversity, ecosystems, disasters, energy, agriculture, health, climate, weather and water. Since the range of the information is so wide, it can be difficult for the users to find exactly what they are looking for. GEOSS has the aim to link all these systems and to provide an easy access for a wide variety of users in both public and private sectors ([GEO 2020a](#)). The users can find existing and planned observing systems from the whole world and everything is accessible at one single Internet access point, the GEOSS Portal. The System of systems helps thereby to access the variety of open data bases, makes it easier for the users to connect to others and it supports the development of new systems for a better understanding of our earth.

2.1 GEOSS Portal

The GEOSS Portal, which is accessible via geoportal.org, operates as an interface between data providers and users who are searching for data. The platform makes the data better visible to the users from all over the world. For the data providers this is a good possibility to spread their data and at the same time they remain the only owner of the shared resources ([Bemmelen et al. 2017](#)). But how is the GEOSS Portal working? When users open the website www.geoportal.org, which was refurbished during 2016 and 2017, a map and a search panel can be seen. On the right side the users can find a series of icons for basic GIS functionalities like Layer handling and a set of basemaps. The upper left corner shows a menu button, with options like search, info, contacting the helpdesk, statistics, terms and conditions and sign-in. The advanced search panel, which can be seen in [figure 2.1](#), gives the user the opportunity to itemize the search. Choosing an Earth observation catalog, itemizing the thematic area and defining the area of interest with the help of a bounding box

or by choosing a country or continent and also defining the timeframe are all options the user can determine. Figure 2.2 shows how it would look like if a user would search for wind data in Europe. After typing wind in the search panel from figure 2.1 the search panel from figure 2.2 is opening. The user has now even more options to narrow the search by, for example, choosing a data format. After choosing one of the data sets, that are shown in the result list, the user has several options.

Figure 2.1: Webiste of the GEOSS Portal (www.geoportal.org) with the advanced search panel

By clicking on the See more button a new window opens with information about the resource. This can be seen in figure 2.3. In this new window the user gets general information about the resource, contact information, data identification and descriptive keywords. Download information or links to the Download Server of the wanted resource can also be found there.

The GEOSS Portal provides an access to a wide range of data bases and portals. For an unexperienced user this can be quite overwhelming in the beginning. Just the search for wind gives more than 12000 result sides with 10 entries on each side. This makes it perhaps difficult for an energy modeller, who is new in this area, to find the right data set. Within LOD-GEOSS we worked on a request that uses the existing tools from GEOSS to select within the high amount of results. In the next Chapter 2.2, this method will be described in more detail.

2.2 Selecting data from the GEOSS Portal

The amount of results, which the user gets in the GEOSS Portal, is quite large. Since it can be difficult to have a look at more than 1000 data sets, the idea was to get the list of results in a machine readable list.

Figure 2.2: An example for a search for wind in the GEOSS-Portal. The different options that the user can select can be seen.

Usually the user just sees the Website of the GEOSS Portal. Behind that stands the GEO Discovery and Access Broker – the GEO DAB. The GEO DAB connects the requests from the users of the GEOSS Portal with the resources of the GEOSS Providers. It is a middleware component which uses different APIs.

To get a machine-readable list from the results, the RESTful API and OpenSearch were used (*GEO API n.d.*). With the GEO DAB it was now, for example, possible to get a list with the results for the search item wind. All the results were now stored in a json file, which made it easier to work further with it. By having a look at the first sides with results for wind in the GEOSS Portal, it can be seen that many of the data sets had a pressure level, like 700 or 250hPa, in the header. Since we had now a machine readable list, it was easy to select maybe just the data sets that had wind and 850hPa in the title. This scaled the number of the results already down. Many data sets had a resolution in the title, which can also be used for selecting out all data sets with 2.5 and 1.5, because this spatial resolution would not be high enough. Another sorting criterion would be the existence of a description. This can be continued for as

Figure 2.3: Detail window at the GEOSS-Portal that can be seen after clicking on the See more button of the wanted data set.

many requirements as the user wants to have. This is still in the testing phase but it is already a good first approach for getting a better overview of the existing data. While working on the requests we also had contact to the GEOSS help desk. It is easy to contact them via Email and they were answering within a short amount of time and were always helpful. The help desk can be found in the menu of the GEOSS Portal. Users can also find videos ¹ about the Portal. More detailed information about GEOSS can be found in Van Bemmelen et al. and on this Website ² everything about the GEO DAB can be found.

If the user found a suitable data set from the result list, the data need to be downloaded in the next step. How this is done will be explained exemplarily for four data sets in the next Chapters.

¹<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCZwhJZI76s7K9eAcBXAPyrw/playlists>

²<https://www.geodab.net/>

3 Using Static Geographical Data

3.1 Corine Land Cover

The CORINE Land Cover dataset¹ is an inventory of land cover in 44 classes. It has a geometric resolution of about 100m and covers the participating countries in Europe. It has been updated in the years 2000, 2006, 2012 and 2018.

The dataset is produced by visual interpretation of high resolution satellite imagery. A few countries apply semi-automatic solutions using national in-situ data. The data is now produced as part of the EU Copernicus programme.

The dataset can be used to classify usable and unusable areas for renewable energy instations.

At detailed description can be found in the CLC user manual²

Figure 3.1: Download area of the COPERNICUS Portal for CORINE Data

Downloading the data requires a user account for the Copernicus system. Once logged in, the data can be found via "Product Portfolio", "Land Cover & Land Use Mapping", "Corine Land Cover".

The portal offers access to INSPIRE metadata and to directly download the data. It is available as GEOTiff, Vector data and a SQL database.

¹<https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/corine-land-cover>

²<https://land.copernicus.eu/user-corner/technical-library/clc-product-user-manual>

3.2 Global Land Cover

The Global Land Cover is a similar dataset as the CORINE data set, covering the whole globe in a coarser resolution of 300 m.

The dataset can be found by searching for "Global Land Cover" in the GEOSS Portal and selecting e.g. the "Global Land Cover Product (2005 to 2006)". A more detailed description and metadata are available with the "show more..." link.

Figure 3.2: Search Result for "Global Land Cover" in the GEOSS Portal

With the yellow downward arrow, the data can directly be downloaded from the GEOSS portal. In this case the download link is a .zip archive with the raster data.

3.3 LUISA Platform

The LUISA Territorial Modelling Platform³ is a platform by the European Commission primarily used for the ex-ante evaluation of EC policies that have a direct or indirect territorial impact.

It is based on the concept of 'land function' for cross-sector integration.

Maps from the LUISA Platform are based e.g. on the CORINE Data set (see section 3.1) which has been improved by higher overall spatial detail and finer thematic breakdown of artificial land uses, it distinguishes e.g. between different residential areas as urban, suburban, commercial and industrial, or share of old and new buildings. It contains also scenario based land use projects into the future.

The data can also be found via the GEOSS Portal by searching for LUISA and filtering the results for the Source "Joint Research Center Data Catalog".

The LUISA platform offers also other dataset sets as

- Average travel distances.
- Atmospheric emissions, PM 2.5, PM 10, NO₂,

³https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/luisa_en

Figure 3.3: Search Results for the LUISA Data Set in the GEOSS Portal

- energy content of dedicated crops
- Biomass harvested from energy crops
- Employment per region

3.4 Elevation

The elevation of the Earth has been measured in great detail by the Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) in 2000-2006. The maps show the elevation above sea level and the depth of the ocean and sea bottom. The data has a resolution of about 90m at the equator. The detailed data from the STRM is between 60° North and 50° South, which covers most of the global land area. Regions further North and further South are covered by the GTOPO30 (Gesch et al. 1999) data set with a resolution of about 1000m at the equator.

The dataset can be found in the GEOSS portal with the keyword "elevation SRTM". It consists of two data sets, one for the Western hemisphere, one for the Eastern hemisphere.

4 Using Time Series Data

4.1 ERA5-hourly data on single levels from 1979 to present

ERA5 is a global climate reanalysis, which combines observations with model data. This data set is a product of the ECMWF and contains many atmospheric, land and ocean climate variables in an hourly resolution. The spatial resolution of this global data set is 30x30km. Uncertainties for all variables are available at a reduced resolution (Copernicus Climate Data Store). For this best practice guide the ERA5.hourly data on single levels from 1979 to present were selected. Variables like, 100m wind, temperatures, solar radiation and many more can be found in this data set and they are easy to access. This makes ERA5 suitable for every energy system modeler. Table 2-1 shows some of the variables and their descriptions that could be of interest for energy system modelers. A description of the whole ERA5 data set and a list of all available variables can be found on the Copernicus Website

Variable-name	Unit	Description
100m u-component of wind	ms-1	This parameter is the eastward component of the 100 m wind. It is the horizontal speed of air moving towards the east, at a height of 100 metres above the surface of the Earth, in metres per second. Care should be taken when comparing model parameters with observations, because observations are often local to a particular point in space and time, rather than representing averages over a model grid box. This parameter can be combined with the northward component to give the speed and direction of the horizontal 100 m wind.

Variable-name	Unit	Description
100m v-component of wind	ms-1	This parameter is the northward component of the 100 m wind. It is the horizontal speed of air moving towards the north, at a height of 100 metres above the surface of the Earth, in metres per second. Care should be taken when comparing model parameters with observations, because observations are often local to a particular point in space and time, rather than representing averages over a model grid box. This parameter can be combined with the eastward component to give the speed and direction of the horizontal 100 m wind.
10m u-component of neutral wind	ms-1	This parameter is the eastward component of the "neutral wind", at a height of 10 metres above the surface of the Earth. The neutral wind is calculated from the surface stress and the corresponding roughness length by assuming that the air is neutrally stratified. The neutral wind is slower than the actual wind in stable conditions, and faster in unstable conditions. The neutral wind is, by definition, in the direction of the surface stress. The size of the roughness length depends on land surface properties or the sea state.
10m u-component of wind	ms-1	This parameter is the eastward component of the 10m wind. It is the horizontal speed of air moving towards the east, at a height of ten metres above the surface of the Earth, in metres per second. Care should be taken when comparing this parameter with observations, because wind observations vary on small space and time scales and are affected by the local terrain, vegetation and buildings that are represented only on average in the ECMWF Integrated Forecasting System (IFS). This parameter can be combined with the V component of 10m wind to give the speed and direction of the horizontal 10m wind.

Variable-name	Unit	Description
10m v-component of neutral wind	ms-1	This parameter is the northward component of the "neutral wind", at a height of 10 metres above the surface of the Earth. The neutral wind is calculated from the surface stress and the corresponding roughness length by assuming that the air is neutrally stratified. The neutral wind is slower than the actual wind in stable conditions, and faster in unstable conditions. The neutral wind is, by definition, in the direction of the surface stress. The size of the roughness length depends on land surface properties or the sea state.
10m v-component of wind	ms-1	This parameter is the northward component of the 10m wind. It is the horizontal speed of air moving towards the north, at a height of ten metres above the surface of the Earth, in metres per second. Care should be taken when comparing this parameter with observations, because wind observations vary on small space and time scales and are affected by the local terrain, vegetation and buildings that are represented only on average in the ECMWF Integrated Forecasting System (IFS). This parameter can be combined with the U component of 10m wind to give the speed and direction of the horizontal 10m wind.
2m temperature	K	This parameter is the temperature of air at 2m above the surface of land, sea or inland waters. 2m temperature is calculated by interpolating between the lowest model level and the Earth's surface, taking account of the atmospheric conditions. This parameter has units of kelvin (K). Temperature measured in kelvin can be converted to degrees Celsius (°C) by subtracting 273.15.

Variable-name	Unit	Description
Mean runoff rate	$kgm^{-2}s^{-1}$	Some water from rainfall, melting snow, or deep in the soil, stays stored in the soil. Otherwise, the water drains away, either over the surface (surface runoff), or under the ground (sub-surface runoff) and the sum of these two is called runoff. This parameter is the mean over a particular time period which depends on the data extracted. It is the rate the runoff would have if it were spread evenly over the grid box. Care should be taken when comparing model parameters with observations, because observations are often local to a particular point rather than averaged over a grid box. Runoff is a measure of the availability of water in the soil, and can, for example, be used as an indicator of drought or flood.

Variable-name	Unit	Description
Surface runoff	m	<p>Some water from rainfall, melting snow, or deep in the soil, stays stored in the soil. Otherwise, the water drains away, either over the surface (surface runoff), or under the ground (sub-surface runoff) and the sum of these two is called runoff. This parameter is accumulated over a particular time period which depends on the data extracted. For the reanalysis, the accumulation period is over the 1 hour up to the validity date and time. For the ensemble members, ensemble mean and ensemble spread, the accumulation period is over the 3 hours up to the validity date and time. The units of runoff are depth in metres of water. This is the depth the water would have if it were spread evenly over the grid box. Care should be taken when comparing model parameters with observations, because observations are often local to a particular point rather than averaged over a grid box. Observations are also often taken in different units, such as mm/day, rather than the accumulated metres produced here. Runoff is a measure of the availability of water in the soil, and can, for example, be used as an indicator of drought or flood.</p>

Variable-name	Unit	Description
Surface net solar radiation	Jm^{-2}	<p>This parameter is the amount of solar radiation (also known as shortwave radiation) that reaches a horizontal plane at the surface of the Earth (both direct and diffuse) minus the amount reflected by the Earth's surface (which is governed by the albedo). Radiation from the Sun (solar, or shortwave, radiation) is partly reflected back to space by clouds and particles in the atmosphere (aerosols) and some of it is absorbed. The remainder is incident on the Earth's surface, where some of it is reflected. This parameter is accumulated over a particular time period which depends on the data extracted. For the reanalysis, the accumulation period is over the 1 hour up to the validity date and time. For the ensemble members, ensemble mean and ensemble spread, the accumulation period is over the 3 hours up to the validity date and time. The units are joules per square metre (Jm^{-2}). To convert to watts per square metre (Wm^{-2}), the accumulated values should be divided by the accumulation period expressed in seconds. The ECMWF convention for vertical fluxes is positive downwards.</p>

Variable-name	Unit	Description
Surface net solar radiation, clear sky	Jm^{-2}	<p>This parameter is the amount of solar (shortwave) radiation reaching the surface of the Earth (both direct and diffuse) minus the amount reflected by the Earth's surface (which is governed by the albedo), assuming clear-sky (cloudless) conditions. It is the amount of radiation passing through a horizontal plane. Clear-sky radiation quantities are computed for exactly the same atmospheric conditions of temperature, humidity, ozone, trace gases and aerosol as the corresponding total-sky quantities (clouds included), but assuming that the clouds are not there. Radiation from the Sun (solar, or shortwave, radiation) is partly reflected back to space by clouds and particles in the atmosphere (aerosols) and some of it is absorbed. The rest is incident on the Earth's surface, where some of it is reflected. The difference between downward and reflected solar radiation is the surface net solar radiation. This parameter is accumulated over a particular time period which depends on the data extracted. For the reanalysis, the accumulation period is over the 1 hour up to the validity date and time. For the ensemble members, ensemble mean and ensemble spread, the accumulation period is over the 3 hours up to the validity date and time. The units are joules per square metre (Jm^{-2}). To convert to watts per square metre (Wm^{-2}), the accumulated values should be divided by the accumulation period expressed in seconds. The ECMWF convention for vertical fluxes is positive downwards.</p>

Variable-name	Unit	Description
Surface solar radiation downwards	Jm^{-2}	<p>This parameter is the amount of solar radiation (also known as shortwave radiation) that reaches a horizontal plane at the surface of the Earth. This parameter comprises both direct and diffuse solar radiation. Radiation from the Sun (solar, or shortwave, radiation) is partly reflected back to space by clouds and particles in the atmosphere (aerosols) and some of it is absorbed. The rest is incident on the Earth's surface (represented by this parameter). To a reasonably good approximation, this parameter is the model equivalent of what would be measured by a pyranometer (an instrument used for measuring solar radiation) at the surface. However, care should be taken when comparing model parameters with observations, because observations are often local to a particular point in space and time, rather than representing averages over a model grid box. This parameter is accumulated over a particular time period which depends on the data extracted. For the reanalysis, the accumulation period is over the 1 hour up to the validity date and time. For the ensemble members, ensemble mean and ensemble spread, the accumulation period is over the 3 hours up to the validity date and time. The units are joules per square metre (Jm^{-2}). To convert to watts per square metre (Wm^{-2}), the accumulated values should be divided by the accumulation period expressed in seconds. The ECMWF convention for vertical fluxes is positive downwards.</p>

Variable-name	Unit	Description
Forecast albedo	Dimensionless	This parameter is a measure of the reflectivity of the Earth’s surface. It is the fraction of solar (shortwave) radiation reflected by Earth’s surface, across the solar spectrum, for both direct and diffuse radiation. The values of this parameter can range between zero and one. Typically, snow and ice have high reflectivity with albedo values of 0.8 and above, land has intermediate values between about 0.1 and 0.4 and the ocean has low values of 0.1 or less. Radiation from the Sun (solar, or shortwave, radiation) is partly reflected back to space by clouds and particles in the atmosphere (aerosols) and some of it is absorbed. The remainder is incident on the Earth’s surface, where some of it is reflected. The portion that is reflected by the Earth’s surface depends on the albedo. In the ECMWF Integrated Forecasting System (IFS), a climatological background albedo (observed values averaged over a period of several years) is used, modified by the model over water, ice and snow. Albedo is often shown as a percentage (%).

Table 4.1: Table of variables of the ERA5-hourly data on single levels from 1979 to present data set that are of interest for energy modellers (Copernicus Climate Data Store).

4.1.1 Data Download

The *ERA5-hourly data on single levels from 1979 to present* can be found in the GEOSS portal ¹. To download the data the user will be forwarded to the Climate Data Store (CDS). Furthermore, the link to the ERA5 documentation ² can be found on the GEOSS Portal (Figure 4.1).

Instructions for how to download the ERA5 data sets via the CDS can be found on the ECMWF website ⁴. The user can choose between the Web Interface and the CDS API Service to retrieve the data. In a first step the user needs to create a CDS account. This can be done here ⁵.

¹<https://www.geoportal.org/?f:phrase=era5&f:dataSource=dab>

²<https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/CKB/ERA5%3A+data+documentation>

⁴<https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/CKB/How+to+download+ERA5>

⁵<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/user/register>

Figure 4.1: The GEOSS Portal³ gives links and information about the ERA5 data set and where it can be downloaded (Last request: july 2020).

CDS web interface

After creating a CDS account⁶ the user has to search for ERA5 in the search box⁷ of the CDS Climate Data Store. Figure 4.3 shows that the list of results contains 26 data sets. As already mentioned the *ERA5-hourly data on single levels from 1979 to present* data set was chosen as an example here. After selecting the desired data set, a side with detailed information appears (figure 4.3).

The user can find there an overview of the data set, the documentation, and some examples and also contact and licence information. For getting the data the *Download data* tab is important now. By clicking on the Download data tab the user will find different boxes. Figure 4.4 shows some of the boxes. The user can select here different parameters that the data set should contain at the end. Those parameters include the product type, the variables, the year, month and day, the geographical area and the format of the data set. The user can choose between GRIB and NetCDF. The latter one works only when the request includes just one variable. If the required data set should contain more than one variable, the user has to choose the GRIB format.

If everything is selected, the data licenses must be accepted in terms of use. Now the download request can be sent via Submit Form. After the request has

⁶<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/user/register?destination=%2F%23!%2Fhome>

⁷<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/#!/home>

Search results

ERA5 **All** Applications Datasets

Sort by **Relevancy** Showing 1-20 of 26 results for ERA5 x

- Title
- Type
- Product type
- Variable domain
- Spatial coverage
- Temporal coverage
- Sector
- Provider

-
Thermal comfort indices derived from ERA5 reanalysis
 Thermal comfort indices derived from ERA5 reanalysis

-
ERA5-Land monthly averaged data from 1981 to present
 ERA5-Land monthly averaged data from 1981 to present

-
ERA5-Land hourly data from 1981 to present
 ERA5-Land hourly data from 1981 to present

-
ERA5 monthly averaged data on pressure levels from 1979 to present
 ERA5 monthly averaged data on pressure levels from 1979 to present

-
ERA5 hourly data on pressure levels from 1979 to present
 ERA5 hourly data on pressure levels from 1979 to present

-
Fire danger indices historical data from the Copernicus Emergency Management Service
 danger indices are calculated using weather forecast from historical simulations provided by ECMWF ERA5

-
Agrometeorological indicators from 1979 to 2018 derived from reanalysis
 -ecological studies. This dataset is based on the hourly ECMWF ERA5 data at surface level and is referred to

Figure 4.2: List of results of ERA5 data sets in the CDS

been processed, the Download button appears. The selected ERA5 data can be downloaded now and the user is now ready to work further with the data.

CDS API

In addition to the CDS web interface it is also possible to use the CDS API for downloading ERA5 data with python scripts.

The first step here is to install the CDS API. Instructions on how to install it are available for linux⁹, Windows¹⁰ and Mac¹¹ users. The procedure for linux users will be explained now.

In the first step an empty file with the name `.cdsapirc` must be created in the user's home directory. The url and API key, which are individual for each user and which can be found by logging in to the CDS, need to be copied into this file. In the next step the *CDS API client*, which is a python based library, needs to be installed with `pip install cdsapi`. After installing the library the user is ready to request datasets from the CDS. The procedure is now almost the same as for the CDS web interface. The user has to select a data set from the CDS¹². In the next step, the user can select the desired parameters under

⁹<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/api-how-to>

¹⁰<https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/CKB/How+to+install+and+use+CDS+API+on+Windows>

¹¹<https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/CKB/How+to+install+and+use+CDS+API+on+macOS>

¹²<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/#!/home>

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ERA5 hourly data on single levels from 1979 to present

Overview
Download data
Quality assessment
Documentation
View

ERA5 is the fifth generation ECMWF atmospheric reanalysis of the global climate. Reanalysis combines model data with observations from across the world into a globally complete and consistent dataset using the laws of physics. This principle, called data assimilation, is based on the method used by numerical weather prediction centres, where every so many hours (12 hours at ECMWF) a previous forecast is combined with newly available observations in an optimal way to produce a new best estimate of the state of the atmosphere, called analysis, from which an updated, improved forecast is issued. Reanalysis works in the same way, but at reduced resolution to allow for the provision of a dataset spanning back several decades. Reanalysis does not have the constraint of issuing timely forecasts, so there is more time to collect observations, and when going further back in time, to allow for the ingestion of improved versions of the original observations, which all benefit the quality of the reanalysis product.

The assimilation system is able to estimate biases between observations and to sift good-quality data from poor data. The laws of physics allow for estimates at locations where data coverage is low, such as for surface temperature in the Arctic. The provision of estimates at each grid point around the globe for each regular output time, over a long period, always using the same format, makes reanalysis a very convenient and popular dataset to work with.

The observing system has changed drastically over time, and although the assimilation system can resolve data holes, the initially much sparser networks will lead to less accurate estimates. For this reason, ERA5 includes an uncertainty estimate that provides guidance on where products are expected to be more and where less accurate.

When complete, ERA5 will contain a detailed record of the evolution of the global atmosphere from 1950 onwards with a total size of about 9 Petabytes. ERA5 will replace the ERA-interim reanalysis, which is now 10 years old.

Although the analysis procedure considers chunks of data in a window of 12 hours in one go, ERA5 provides estimates for each hour of the day, worldwide. This is made possible by the 4D-Var assimilation method, which takes account of the exact timing of the observations and model evolution within the assimilation window. This hourly output resolution is quite an improvement with respect to ERA-Interim, and provides a more detailed evolution of particular weather events.

Variables are produced at the surface and on model levels but are also interpolated to three other level types: pressure levels, potential temperature levels and one potential vorticity level. In order to make data access more manageable, the ERA5 dataset has been split into

Contact

copernicus-support@ecmwf.int

Licence

[Licence to use Copernicus Products](#)

Publication date

2018-06-14

References

DOI: [10.24381/cds.adbb2d47](https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.adbb2d47)

Related data

- [ERA5 hourly data on pressure levels from 1979 to present](#)
- [ERA5 monthly averaged data on pressure levels from 1979 to present](#)
- [ERA5 monthly averaged data on single levels from 1979 to present](#)

Figure 4.3: Information about the selected ERA5 data set that can be found at the Website of the CDS⁸ (Last request: july 2020)

the Download Data tab (Figure ??and 4.4). At the bottom of this site the user will find the button Show API request (Figure 4.5).

By clicking on that button the API request will be shown. This text needs to be copied into an empty file and saved as a `.py` file. By running this file with python you can download the data. An ERA5 API request example can be seen in Figure 4.6. The user can also create their own API by following the syntax in Figure 4.7. It is also necessary to agree to the Terms of Use when using the CDS API.

4.1.2 Converting GRIB to NetCDF

The ERA5 data can be downloaded as NetCDF or GRIB files. NetCDF can only be chosen when just one variable is required. In the case that the user wants to have several variables within one file than it is necessary to select the GRIB format. For further processing it is recommended to convert the GRIB file into NetCDF. This can be done with python. First install the `cfrib` package with `pip install cfrib` or `conda install -c conda-forge cfrib`. (In the case that an error occurs, try to install this: `conda install -c conda-forge eccodes`). After installing the package, it is just needed to run the following lines (figure 4.8:

The data are now converted to NetCDF. ECMWF lists on its website¹³ many other tools for working with GRIB data.

¹³<https://confluence.ecmwf.int/pages/viewpage.action?pageId=55122386>

Figure 4.4: Downloading an ERA5 data set from the CDS. The web interface makes it easy to select the parameters that are needed.

4.2 CAMS

In this section the second and third data set, which are both products of CAMS, are presented. The Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS)) is a service that is implemented by the ECMWF and one of six services that form Copernicus. The Earth observation programme Copernicus has as a main goal to provide high quality information about the earth from satellite data, ground-based, airborne and seaborne measurements. More information about Copernicus can be found here¹⁴. A short and compact description about CAMS and its different parts was written by Marion Schroedter-Homscheidt in the Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) Radiation Service in a nutshell (Schroedter-Homscheidt et al. 2017):

4.2.1 CAMS in a Nutshell

All Sky Radiation in a Nutshell

The atmosphere service of Copernicus combines state-of-the-art atmospheric modelling on aerosols with Earth observation data to provide information services covering European air quality, global atmospheric composition, climate, and UV and solar energy. The CAMS Radiation Service provides a fast parameterisation of the radiative transfer in the atmosphere (figure 4.9) and couples cloud-free sky parameters as aerosols, water vapour, and ozone with satellite-based cloud information (figure 4.10).

Within the radiation service, existing historical and daily updated databases HelioClim-3 and SOLEMI for monitoring incoming surface solar irradiance are further developed. The new service is jointly provided by DLR, Armines, and Transvalor. The Monitoring Atmospheric Composition and Climate (MACC)

¹⁴<https://www.copernicus.eu/en/about-copernicus>

Geographical area ?

Whole available region
With this option selected the entire available area will be provided

Sub-region extraction ?

North: 90
South: -90
West: -180
East: 180

Format

GRIB NetCDF (experimental) Clear all

Show API request Show Toolbox request Login/register to submit request

Figure 4.5: Downloading an ERA5 data set from the CDS. After selecting the needed parameters the API request can be created at the bottom of the website.

project series have been prepared for the service provision, which is now operational as part of the Copernicus programme.

Clear Sky Radiation in a Nutshell

The fast clear-sky model called Copernicus McClear implements a fully physical modelling replacing empirical relations or simpler models used before. It exploits the recent results on aerosol properties and total column content in water vapour and ozone produced by the Copernicus service. It provides irradiances that would be observed in cloud-free conditions. Data are made available both via the Copernicus and the SoDa portal ([Schroedter-Homscheidt et al. 2017](#)).

The user can choose between two products from the radiation service which are the CAMS time series and the CAMS AGATE (Europe) and JADE (Africa) data sets. By choosing the time series the user gets the opportunity to determine the locations for which he wants the time series to be calculated by the CAMS Radiation Service. Furthermore the time steps, which are ranging from 1minute to 1month, can be selected by the user ([Schroedter-Homscheidt et al. 2017](#)). The AGATE data set can be received at a fixed grid over Europe with a temporal

```

api_era5.py
~/Daten/ERA5
File Edit View Search Tools Documents Help
#!/usr/bin/envs/cdsapi python
import cdsapi

c = cdsapi.Client()
c.retrieve(
    'reanalysis-era5-single-levels',
    {
        'product_type': 'reanalysis',
        'variable': [
            '100m_u_component_of_wind', '100m_v_component_of_wind', '2m_temperature',
        ],
        'year': '1993',
        'month': [
            '01', '02', '03',
        ],
        'day': [
            '01', '02', '03',
            '04', '05', '06',
            '07', '08', '09',
            '10', '11', '12',
            '13', '14', '15',
        ],
        'time': [
            '00:00', '01:00', '02:00',
            '03:00', '04:00', '05:00',
            '06:00',
        ],
        'format': 'grib',
    },
    '/home/Data/ERA5/era5.grib')
    
```

Figure 4.6: Example for a CDS API request for the selected ERA5 data set.

resolution of 15minutes. Both data sets are described in more detail now in sections 4.2.2 and 4.2.3.

4.2.2 Time Series

The CAMS time series consists mostly of radiation variables but it includes also all atmospheric input parameters used for clouds, aerosols, ozone, water vapour, non-bias corrected irradiation values and the surface reflective properties. Table 3-1 shows all the available variables.

The data cover Europe, Africa, the Atlantic Ocean and the Middle East (-66° to 66° in latitudes and longitudes). Within this area the user can define the locations for which he wants the time series to be interpolated. Furthermore the user can choose the temporal resolution which is available for 1minute, 15minutes, 1hour, 1 day or 1 month. The temporal period spans the time from the 01.02.2004 up to two days ago (Wald et al. 2015). For further information of the time series have a look at the CAMS website¹⁵.

Variable name	Abbreviation/ID	Unit
Irradiation on horizontal plane at the top of atmosphere	TOA	Whm^{-2}

¹⁵<http://www.soda-pro.com/de/web-services/radiation/cams-radiation-service/info>

Variable name	Abbreviation/ID	Unit
Clear sky global irradiation on horizontal plane at ground level	Clear sky GHI	Whm^{-2}
Clear sky beam irradiation on horizontal plane at ground level	Clear sky BHI	Whm^{-2}
Clear sky diffuse irradiation on horizontal plane at ground level	Clear sky DHI	Whm^{-2}
Clear sky beam irradiation on mobile plane following the sun at normal incidence	Clear sky BNI	Whm^{-2}
Global irradiation on horizontal plane at ground level	GHI	Whm^{-2}
Beam irradiation on horizontal plane at ground level	BHI	Whm^{-2}
Diffuse irradiation on horizontal plane at ground level	DHI	Whm^{-2}
Beam irradiation on mobile plane following the sun at normal incidence	BNI	Whm^{-2}
Proportion of reliable data in the summarization	Reliability	0-1
Solar zenithal angle for the middle of the summarization	sza	deg
1.0 means summer, 0.0 means winter	Summer/winter split	0,1
Total column content of ozone	tco3	Dobson unit
Total column content of water vapor	tcwv	Kgm^{-2}
Partial aerosol optical depth at 550 nm for black carbon	AOD BC	
Partial aerosol optical depth at 550 nm for dust	AOD DU	
Partial aerosol optical depth at 550 nm for sea salt	AOD SS	
Partial aerosol optical depth at 550 nm for organic matter	AOD OR	
Partial aerosol optical depth at 550 nm for sulphate	AOD SU	
Partial aerosol optical depth at 550 nm for nitrate	AOD NI	
Partial aerosol optical depth at 550 nm for ammonium	AOD AM	
Angstroem coefficient for aerosol	Alpha	
Ground albedo	Albedo	

Variable name	Abbreviation/ID	Unit
value of the nearest acquisition time of the pixel	Cloud optical depth	
Cloud coverage of the pixel (percentage from 0 to 100, value of the nearest acquisition time of the pixel) -1=no value	Cloud coverage	Percentage
Cloud type (value of the nearest acquisition time of the pixel) - 1=no value 0=no clouds 5=low-level cloud 6=medium-level cloud 7=high-level cloud 8=thin cloud	Cloud type	
Global irradiation without bias correction on horizontal plane at ground level	GHI no corr	Whm^{-2}
Beam irradiation without bias correction on horizontal plane at ground level	BHI no corr	Whm^{-2}
Diffuse irradiation without bias correction on horizontal plane at ground level	DHI no corr	Whm^{-2}
Beam irradiation without bias correction on mobile plane following the sun at normal incidence	BNI no corr	Whm^{-2}

Table 4.2: Variables of the CAMS time series

Data Download

Downloading the time series of the CAMS radiation service is for free and requires only a registration on the website. Users need to agree to the CAMS data policy before sending a request. There are two options to get access to the data.

WPS

The first one is the WPS standard with which the user can invoke geospatial data. In this catalogue¹⁶ the services are described. If the user doesn't want to use that it is also possible to do it by hand as shown below:

```
curl -o output.xml -v -d @test_mcclear_params.xml
-H "Content-Type: text/xml"
http://www.soda-is.com/service/wps
```

or

```
curl -o output.xml -v -d @test_cams_radiation_params.xml
-H "Content-Type: text/xml"
http://www.soda-is.com/service/wps.
```

¹⁶<http://www.soda-is.com/service/wps?SERVICE=WPS&request=GetCapabilities>

```
import cdsapi

c= cdsapi.Client()

c.retrieve("dataset-short-name",
           {... subselection request ...},
           "target-file")
```

Figure 4.7: Syntax of the CDS API request (Copernicus Climate Data Store)

```
import cfrib
ds = xr.open_dataset("era5_data.grib", engine="cfrib")
ds.to netcdf("/home/place_to_save_nc/era5_data.nc")
```

Figure 4.8: Convertig GRIB to NetCDF

The output file *output.xml* contains the URL of the result. *Test_mcclear_params.xml* or *test_cams_radiation_params.xml* is the input file (Wald et al. 2015). The user has to select the inputs, which are the geographical coordinates of the site of interest, the elevation above sea-level of the requested site and the period of time. The User Guide to the CAMS Radiation Service (CRS) 2019 contains a more detailed description and the SoDa website¹⁷ provides more examples. Figure 4.11 shows one of those examples for the input curl.

WGET The second option to download the data is wget which is a program for retrieving data (Wald et al. 2015). In a first step the user needs to download wget.exe into a directory. The second step is to create a text file in the same directory and copy-paste the following information in a single line:

```
wget -O CAMS-radiation_Carpentras_2017-01-01_2017-01-05.csv
http://www.soda-is.com/service/wps?
Service=WPS&Request=Execute&Identifier=get_cams_radiation
&version=1.0.0&DataInputs=latitude=44.083;longitude=5.059;altitude=-999;
date_begin=2017-01-01;date_end=2017-01-05;time_ref=UT;summarization=PT15M;
username=myemailaddress%%2540mycompany.com
&RawDataOutput=irradiation
```

The myemailaddress%%2540mycompany.com needs to be the users email address. As already mentioned for the WPS the user also needs to define variables like latitude, longitude and time when using wget. The full list of variables that needs to be defined by the user and a more detailed description can be found at the SoDa Website. Due to safety and stability reasons every user has a re-

¹⁷<http://www.soda-pro.com/de/help/cams-services/cams-radiation-service/automatic-access#wget>

Figure 4.9: Principle of radiative transfer which is the basis of the CAMS Radiation Service

stricted amount of 75 requests for the time series per day ([MINES ParisTech 2020](#)).

4.2.3 CAMS AGATE

The CAMS AGATE data set includes data on a fixed grid over Europe. The user can choose between eight radiation components:

- Global Horizontal Irradiation (GHI)
- Beam (direct) Horizontal Irradiation (BHI)
- Diffuse Horizontal Irradiation (DHI)
- Beam (direct) Normal Irradiation (BNI)
- Global Horizontal Irradiation in clear sky conditions (Gc)
- Beam (direct) Horizontal Irradiation in clear sky conditions (BHI)
- Diffuse Horizontal Irradiation in clear sky conditions (DHI)
- Beam (direct) Normal Irradiation in clear sky conditions (BNI)

The radiation components have a temporal resolution of 15minutes and span a temporal period of 2005 to 2018. There exists one hdf5 file per year for each component. The spatial resolution of the data is 0,2° ([Schroedter-Homscheidt](#)

Figure 4.10: Combination of satellite-based cloud information with model based aerosol, water vapour and ozone information to derive time series of solar radiation at the surface in cloudy and cloud-free conditions.

et al. 2017). A more detailed description of AGATE can be found on the SoDa website¹⁸. Figure 4.12 shows the Global Horizontal Irradiation (GHI) over Europe for the 01.04.2005, which is one of the AGATE components.

Data Download

The AGATE data set is available on the SoDa website¹⁹. For retrieving the data the user needs to write an email-request to the following address: support-sales@soda-is.com. After sending the request the user will receive a link that comes with a username and a password which is valid for seven days. On the provided website the user will find one hdf5 file per year for each of the 8 variables. One file has a size of approximately 250MB.

4.3 ECMWF

The European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), which is based in Reading, United Kingdom, is an independent intergovernmental organisation that is supported by 34 states. They have one of the largest super-computer complexes in Europe and one of the largest archives of meteorological data in the world. On their supercomputer systems, ECMWF runs, among others, global numerical weather predictions (NWP) (ECMWF). The NWP model

¹⁸<http://www.soda-pro.com/de/help/cams-services/cams-radiation-service/download-europe-volume>

¹⁹<http://www.soda-pro.com/bg/help/cams-services/cams-radiation-service/download-europe-volume>

```

<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8" standalone="true"?>
- <wps:Execute xmlns:wps="http://www.opengis.net/wps/1.0.0" xsi:schemaLocation="http://www.opengis.net/wps/1.0.0 http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" xmlns:xlink="http://www.w3.org/1999/xlink">
  <ows:Identifier>get_cams_radiation</ows:Identifier>
  - <wps>DataInputs>
    - <wps:Input>
      <ows:Identifier>latitude</ows:Identifier>
      - <wps:Data>
        <wps:LiteralData>44.083</wps:LiteralData>
      </wps:Data>
    </wps:Input>
    - <wps:Input>
      <ows:Identifier>longitude</ows:Identifier>
      - <wps:Data>
        <wps:LiteralData>5.059</wps:LiteralData>
      </wps:Data>
    </wps:Input>
    - <wps:Input>
      <ows:Identifier>altitude</ows:Identifier>
      - <wps:Data>
        <wps:LiteralData>-999</wps:LiteralData>
      </wps:Data>
    </wps:Input>
    - <wps:Input>
      <ows:Identifier>date_begin</ows:Identifier>
      - <wps:Data>
        <wps:LiteralData>2017-01-01</wps:LiteralData>
      </wps:Data>
    </wps:Input>
    - <wps:Input>
      <ows:Identifier>date_end</ows:Identifier>
      - <wps:Data>
        <wps:LiteralData>2017-01-05</wps:LiteralData>
      </wps:Data>
    </wps:Input>
    - <wps:Input>
      <ows:Identifier>time_ref</ows:Identifier>
      - <wps:Data>
        <wps:LiteralData>

```

Figure 4.11: Example for a WPS Input request for a CAMS time series ([MINES ParisTech 2020](#))

Figure 4.12: GHI on the 01.04.2005 from 11:45h to 12:00h from the AGATE data set. Values over the sea are not computed ([MINES ParisTech 2020](#))

can be divided into two forecast types, deterministic and probabilistic forecasts. Section 4.3.1 deals with the first type, the deterministic ones. The probabilistic forecasts and examples of probabilistic forecasts from the ECMWF will be described in section 4.3.2.

4.3.1 ECMWF deterministic forecasts

Numerical weather predictions have the goal to determine the state of the atmosphere for a point at a time in the future as accurate as possible. The quality of the NWP is dependent on many factors. One of them is the knowledge about the current condition of the atmosphere. This information will be used by a set of hydrodynamic equations that are combined with numerical methods within the NWP. Observations of wind, temperature, pressure and many other meteorological variables can describe the initial conditions best but they are not at all times and at every point on earth available. To get a good result anyway, the ECMWF is using data assimilation ([ECMWF n.d.a](#)). Observations and short-range forecasts are combined within the data assimilation to get the best possible initial atmospheric state. Within deterministic forecasts, the model uses only one initial state of the atmosphere to calculate one forecast for the weather of the future ([Casado et al. 2016](#))

HRES

The NWP model of ECMWF is called Integrated Forecast System (IFS) (ECMWF 2020)). The deterministic product of this model is called High Resolution Forecast (HRES) and it provides a more detailed description of the future weather than the ENS which will be described in Chapter 4.2.1. HRES contains forecasts for up to 10 days with a spatial resolution of 9 km and 137 vertical levels. This high resolution, a very detailed orography and the good discrimination of land-sea differences are the advantages of HRES compared to ENS. On the other hand any individual forecast of HRES is mostly not as skilful as the results of the ENS member forecast (Owens & Hewson 2018).

The HRES product contains 4 forecast runs per day at 00, 06, 12 and 18 UTC. Energy modellers will probably find all the needed variables in this data set. Some of the meteorological variables that can be found in the HRES product are listed in Table 4.3 (Owens & Hewson 2018). A more detailed description of the HRES product and a complete list of the variables can be found on the ECMWF Website²⁰.

Compared to the CAMS and ERA5 data, the access to the HRES data is not completely open. For ECMWF members and their co-operating states historical forecasts which are older than 48 hours are available. To get access to the data the user needs a MARS account which can be obtained by contacting the Computing Representative²¹.

Variable name	Abbreviation/ID	Unit
Albedo	al / 174	0-1
Soil type	slt/43	1-7
Total cloud cover	tcc/164	0-1
10 metre U-wind component	10u/165	ms^{-1}
10 metre V-wind-component	10v/166	ms^{-1}
100 metre U wind component	100u/228246	ms^{-1}
100 metre V wind component	100v/228247	ms^{-1}
200 metre U wind component	200u/228239	ms^{-1}
200 metre V wind component	200v/228240	ms^{-1}
Surface runoff	sro/8	m
Direct solar radiation	dsrp/47	Jm^{-2}
Downward UV radiation at the surface	uvb/57	Jm^{-2}
Surface net solar radiation	ssr/176	Jm^{-2}
Surface net solar radiation clear sky	ssrc/210	Jm^{-2}

Table 4.3: Meteorological variables which can be found in the HRES data set and which are suitable for energy modellers (ECMWF 2018).

²⁰<https://www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts/datasets/set-i>

²¹<https://www.ecmwf.int/en/about/contact-us/computing-representatives>

Figure 4.13: Ensemble of a probabilistic forecast. Small differences in the initial conditions can lead to big differences in the forecast due to the chaotic system of the atmosphere ([DWD n.d.](#)).

4.3.2 ECMWF probabilistic forecasts

The atmosphere as well as the ocean are no stable systems, quite the contrary, they are chaotic dynamical systems. This makes it difficult to make a precise forecast since already small changes can have a big impact. Deterministic forecasts have only one value as an output which makes it more difficult to reflect the chaotic system. Probabilistic forecast on the other hand are using several runs with slightly different initial conditions and have a probability as an output. This ensemble forecast allows modelling different states of the weather and makes the uncertainty of the forecast and the range that the future weather can have more visible to the user. Figure 4.13 illustrates that small differences in initial conditions of the ensemble can lead to large differences in the forecast of the weather ([ECMWF n.d.](#)) ([DWD n.d.](#)).

ENS

The Ensemble forecast ENS is, as well as the HRES, a configuration of the IFS. The ENS consists of an ensemble of 51 forecasts and is run two times per day. One of the members is an unperturbed member, the control run (CTRL). The other 50 are perturbed members with perturbed initial states and model physics. This helps the user to see the range of uncertainty in the forecasts and to see the range that the possible future weather can have ([Owens & Hewson 2018](#)). This is one of the biggest differences to the HRES. With a horizontal resolution of 18 km and 91 vertical levels it has a smaller resolution than HRES but the ENS has a forecasting horizon of 15 days. ([Owens & Hewson 2018](#)). Energy modellers will find in the ENS data set, which is available in the GRIB format, the same variables of the atmospheric fields as in the HRES product

(ECMWF 2018). The ENS product provides additional the probabilities of the occurrence of weather events at each grid point. The whole list of available variables can be found here²². To access the ENS product the user needs, as well as for the HRES data, a MARS-account. ECMWF also provides data sets that are open accessible for the public without creating a MARS account. This will be explained in the next Chapter.

Public Data Sets

Not all of ECMWF products are accessible to the public but the user can also find open data sets that are easy to access. The list of public data sets²³ contains many global reanalysis, like for example the ERA-Interim data but also regional reanalysis and atmospheric compositions. Forecast products can also be found in the list, like the TIGGE data. How users can download the public data sets will be explained on the TIGGE data in the next section.

TIGGE

The International Grand Global Ensemble (TIGGE) is a public product from the ECMWF and is therefore accessible for every user. Ensemble forecasts from twelve global NWP centres, like UKMO and NCEP, are combined within the TIGGE data set since October 2006. This data set was developed within the world weather research programme THORPEX which was working on the improvements in the accuracy of 1- day to 2 week weather forecasts (Mladek 2016). Since this data set is open to the public the number of variables is smaller compared to HRES or ENS. Users find a smaller amount of radiation variables and only 10m but not 100m wind values in the TIGGE data but it is still an interesting data set for energy modellers (Mladek 2016)(ECMWF 2019). Table 4.4 shows all the variables that the user receives by downloading the TIGGE data.

Variable name	Abbreviation/ID	Unit
Geopotential height	gh	Gpm
Specific humidity	q	$Kgkg^{-1}$
Temperature	t	K
U-velocity	u	ms^{-1}
V-velocity	v	ms^{-1}
Potential vorticity	pv	$Km2kg^{-1}s^{-1}$
10 meter u-velocity	10u	ms^{-1}
10 meter v-velocity	10v	ms^{-1}
Convective available potential energy	cape	Jkg^{-1}
Convective inhibition	ci	Jkg^{-1}
Field capacity	cap	kgm^{-3}
Land-sea mask	lsm	Proportion

²²<https://www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts/datasets/set-iii>

²³<https://apps.ecmwf.int/datasets/>

Variable name	Abbreviation/ID	Unit
Mean sea level pressure	msl	Pa
Orography	orog	gpm
Skin temperature	skt	K
Snow depth water equivalent	sd	kgm^{-2}
Snow fall water equivalent	sf	kgm^{-2}
Soil moisture	sm	kgm^{-3}
Soil temperature	st	K
Sunshine duration	sund	s
Surface air dew point temperature	2d	K
Surface air maximum temperature	mx2t6	K
Surface air minimum temperature	mn2t6	K
Surface air temperature	2t	K
Surface pressure	sp	Pa
Time-integrated outgoing long wave radiation	ttr	$Wm^{-2}s$
Time-integrated surface latent heat flux	slhf	$Wm^{-2}s$
Time-integrated surfacesolar radiation	ssr	$Wm^{-2}s$
Time-integrated surface net thermal radiation	str	$Wm^{-2}s$
Time-integrated surface sensible heat flux	sshf	$Wm^{-2}s$
Total cloud cover	tcc	%
Total column water	tcw	kgm^{-2}
Total precipitation	tp	kgm^{-2}
Wilting point	wilt	kgm^{-3}

Table 4.4: Variables of the TIGGE data set (Mladek 2016)(ECMWF 2019)

Data Download

The TIGGE data set can be found on the GEOSS-Portal as shown in Figure 4.14. To get access to the data the user first need to create an account on the ECWMF website²⁴. After the registration the data can be requested with an API. This is similar to the CDS API described in Chapter 2.1.2. In a first step the user needs to save an empty file in the Home directory as `.ecmwfapirc`. Into this file the user has to write his API key credentials which can be found here²⁵ or here²⁶. The next step is to install the API client with `pip install ecmwf-api-client`. After installing the library the user is ready to request one of the public datasets²⁷. By choosing one dataset the user can select which kind of data is needed. Several parameters as the month of year, the amount of steps,

²⁴<https://apps.ecmwf.int/registration/>

²⁵<https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/WEBAPI/Access+ECMWF+Public+Datasets>

²⁶<https://api.ecmwf.int/v1/key/>

²⁷<https://apps.ecmwf.int/datasets/>

Figure 4.14: The TIGGE data set can be found in the GEOSS Portal

the calculation times and also the variables can be selected. A small part of this selection side of the TIGGE data set is shown in figure 4.15.

At the bottom of the side with the parameters the user finds two buttons. This can be seen in Figure 4.16. The first one is *Retrive GRIB*. By clicking on that one the user can directly download the data as a GRIB file. The second one says *View data retrieval request*. By clicking on this one the user will get the Python script for the request. This text needs to be copied and pasted into an empty file, which can be named for example *tigge.py*. It is important to change the target entry with the directory where the user want the data to be saved and the name that the data file should have at the end (figure 4.17). This file needs to have the ending *.grib*, since the data have the GRIB format. Now the *tigge.py* file needs to be run within your ECMWF-API environment with *python tigge.py*. It can now take some time until the data are downloaded. On the ECMWF-Website²⁸ the download process is also explained. Users can also find there script examples for the by ECMWF provided public data sets.

²⁸<https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/WEBAPI/Access+ECMWF+Public+Datasets>

Figure 4.15: Download TIGGE data from ECMWF. Several parameter can be selected by the user.

Figure 4.16: Downloading TIGGE data from ECMWF. After choosing the wanted parameters the user can download the data directly (Retrieve GRIB) or get the data retrieval request.

request

Estimated number of fields: 540

[Python script](#) [MARS request](#)

For more information on how to retrieve data programmatically, in Python, please go to [Access ECMWF Public Datasets](#).

```
#!/usr/bin/env python
from ecmwfapi import ECMWFDataServer
server = ECMWFDataServer()
server.retrieve({
    "class": "ti",
    "dataset": "tigge",
    "date": "2018-06-01/to/2018-06-30",
    "expver": "prod",
    "grid": "0.5/0.5",
    "levtype": "sfc",
    "origin": "babj/ecmf/kwbc",
    "param": "136/165/166/167/176/177",
    "step": "24",
    "time": "00:00:00",
    "type": "cf",
    "target": "output",
})
```

Figure 4.17: Data retrieval request that the user gets by clicking choosing View data retrieval request (figure 4.16).

5 Interfacing the Databus and LOD-GEOSS

A direct coupling of the searches on the Databus and the GEOSS catalog could not be realized, because GEOSS does not have a uniform data description and a uniform vocabulary. During the construction of GEOSS, care was taken to integrate as many data sets as possible, and no uniform vocabulary was defined.

In order to facilitate the search within GEOSS, a script was programmed with which the extensive search results can be narrowed down iteratively in order to be able to identify relevant data sets in a more targeted manner. Based on this script, relevant GEOSS datasets were identified to be registered in parallel in the Databus based on the terminology of the Open Energy Ontology, so that they can be found more easily within the domain of energy system analysis.

The procedure was documented so that updates on the databus can be easily performed.

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